

MENTAL HEALTH LITERACY, SERVICES AND PROGRAMS IN UNIVERSITIES: TOWARDS DEVELOPING A SCHOOL MENTAL HEALTH POLICY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 20

Issue 4

Pages: 362-388

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1867

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11392148

Manuscript Accepted: 05-04-2024

Mental Health Literacy, Services and Programs in Universities: Towards Developing A School Mental Health Policy

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Abstract

The prevalence of mental health disorders has been a growing concern and significantly impacts society. As such, it is vital for academic institutions to contribute to the solution of this timely issue. Studies have emphasized the importance of mental health literacy in promoting awareness of mental health, early detection of mental disorders, reducing stigma, providing appropriate assistance to those in need and in developing mental health programs and policies. To this end, the present study employed a mixed-method approach that assessed selected universities' mental health literacy and mental health services. Specifically, mental health literacy levels were analyzed among 342 students, 48 faculty members, 44 employees, and 8 administrators. Results indicated that the participants showed high levels of mental health literacy in all factors, specifically in knowledge of mental health problems, erroneous beliefs or stereotypes, self-help strategies and first-aid skills, and help-seeking behavior. However, focus group interviews revealed a need for improvement in the mental health programs and/or services currently provided in the universities. In light of these findings, a proposed school mental health policy called "GINHAWA" was recommended to enhance the university's mental health programs and services. The results of this study contribute to the literature on mental health literacy and provide practical implications for the development and improvement of mental health programs in academic institutions.

Keywords: *mental health, mental health literacy, mental health services, mental health programs, school mental health policy*

Introduction

"There is no physical health without mental health". - Dr. Brock Christholm (n.d.)

The ancient Romans embraced the idea of "mens sana in corpore sano," which translates to "a sound mind in a sound body." (Young, 2005). This concept emphasizes the importance of nurturing both our physical and mental well-being. Neglecting either one can hinder our overall growth and development as individuals, regardless of age. Therefore, it is crucial to prioritize mental health care as we do with our physical health. A holistic approach to self-care can lead to a healthier and happier life.

Stress, pressure, and other environmental factors have been found to significantly impact the mental health of individuals. Students are particularly susceptible to these challenges, as they may not have developed effective coping mechanisms to manage their stress. According to a 2001 report by the World Health Organization (WHO), mental and neurological disorders affect approximately one in five individuals at some point in their lives. Additionally, the National Alliance on Mental Illness (NAMI) has reported that more than 20% of young people between the ages of 13 and 18 experience mental disorders, with around 13% of children aged 8-15 also affected.

A recent global study conducted by the WHO among 8,761 participants in grades 7-9 (aged 13-17) found that 11% of the respondents had considered suicide, while 16% had attempted suicide due to mental health concerns. These alarming statistics highlight the need for increased awareness and support for mental health issues, particularly among young people. Because of the alarming rate of mental health issues and their effects, many agencies- local or international, State and even non-State agencies have taken action in spreading mental health awareness which aims to increase the mental health literacy of people. Different mental health programs and policies were enacted and implemented as an intervention to this serious problem.

Despite the growing concern over mental health issues, the effectiveness of current initiatives in addressing these problems remains unclear. The rising statistics indicate that more needs to be done to address mental health challenges, particularly among students. Moreover, there is a pressing need to investigate the preparedness of universities to implement mental health programs and provide the necessary support services to stakeholders.

School administrators play an important role in addressing mental health concerns in schools. First, they have the power and authority to create a safe, and supportive environment that promotes mental health and well-being. By nurturing a culture of openness, empathy, understanding, and acceptance, administrators can contribute to reducing or even eradicating stigma to mental health issues and encouraging help-seeking behavior. They can create and implement policies and projects that prioritize the mental health of students which creates an environment where school stakeholders especially students feel safe, supported, accepted, and understood.

Second, administrators are also responsible for resource allocation within the school. They can ensure that there are sufficient mental health professionals available to help the students and other stakeholders. Third, administrators can provide necessary training for teachers and staff on mental health awareness and intervention. By allocating resources appropriately, administrators enhance the capacity of the school to address mental health concerns effectively.

Lastly, administrators can forge linkages or partnerships with mental health agencies, organizations, and other resources. By creating these connections, they can ensure that school stakeholders would have access to additional support services additional to what the school can provide.

By actively fulfilling these roles, administrators contribute to fostering a mentally healthy school environment and providing effective support for students, faculty, and employees' mental well-being.

This study aims to shed light on these questions by examining universities' existing mental health initiatives and evaluating their effectiveness. Through a comprehensive literature review and analysis of current mental health services in universities, the study will help identify gaps and limitations in the current approaches to mental health care. Additionally, this research will help develop a school mental health policy.

Exploring the mental health issues will provide insights into the current state of mental health initiatives in universities and offer recommendations for improving mental health care delivery in academic settings.

Research Questions

Understanding the mental health literacy level of school stakeholders is a crucial step toward creating effective mental health programs and services. This process allows the author of the program for targeted education, reduced stigma, effective communication, and sustainable outcomes. This ensures a well- designed, responsive, and relevant program. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the prevailing level of mental health literacy of the different categories of participants in terms of:
 - 1.1 knowledge about mental health problems;
 - 1.2 erroneous beliefs/stereotypes;
 - 1.3 first-aid skills and help-seeking behavior; and
 - 1.4 self-help strategies?
2. Is there a significant difference in the level of mental health literacy of the participants?
3. How do the factors identified as causes of mental health problems connect to the results of mental health literacy?
4. How does the level of mental health literacy impact the delivery of mental health services available in universities?
5. What suggestions were shared to improve the mental health programs or services?
6. Based on the results of the study, what School Mental Health Policy should be developed?

Methodology

This section presents an overview of the research methods utilized in the study. It encompasses details on the participants, selection process, and research location. The chapter delves into the research design and the rationale behind it. Moreover, it elucidates the instrument used for gathering data and the corresponding procedures. The data analysis techniques and ethical considerations are also expounded in this chapter.

Research Design

The researcher conducted a mixed-method convergent triangulation design. Creswell (2003) describes this kind of research as a research design that involves collecting and analyzing both quantitative and qualitative data at the same time, one after the other. The aim is to triangulate the findings from both data types to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of the research topic. In this design, the researcher collects both types of data at the same time and analyzes them separately using appropriate methods. The results are then converged or integrated by comparing and contrasting them to identify similarities, differences, and inconsistencies.

Comparing and contrasting quantitative and qualitative data in convergent mixed methods involves examining the similarities and differences between numerical and non-numerical information to gain a comprehensive understanding of a research topic. Integrating the analysis of both data types allows for a more robust and holistic interpretation of findings, providing deeper insights and enhancing the overall research validity. The approach can be used in three ways: equal importance design, qualitative dominance design, and quantitative dominance design. In the integration of results, a comparison and contrast approach are used to identify commonalities, disparities, and discrepancies among the findings, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the research outcomes. This process helps to uncover patterns, themes, or relationships that emerge from the analysis of different data sources, contributing to a richer and more nuanced interpretation of the overall research findings. This design is powerful as it integrates both types of data to provide a more complete understanding of the research topic. It is particularly useful as the researcher explored the richness of qualitative data while also providing statistical evidence through quantitative data.

As both data will support each other in addressing the main problem of this study, it was conducted simultaneously, though one after the other without analyzing the results of the other before conducting the data gathering of the other.

For the Quantitative data collection, the Mental Health Literacy questionnaire (MHLq) was administered. MHLq is a validated instrument that measures participants' knowledge and understanding of mental health. The survey contains a set of questions that

inquire about participants' views on mental health, their familiarity with mental health disorders, and their attitudes towards individuals dealing with mental health issues. For the Qualitative data collection, semi-structured focus group interviews were designed to gather in-depth information about the participants' perceptions of mental health, the causes of mental health illnesses, and the mental health programs or services offered at their university. The interviews were conducted by the researcher who is a licensed mental health professional who asked the participants questions related to mental health and probed for additional information.

For the data analysis, the quantitative results, data were computed for analysis using means and the Kruskal-Wallis test to identify the significant difference in the level of mental health literacy of the participants categorized by students, employees, faculty, and administrators. For the qualitative results, thematic analysis was conducted to encapsulate into themes the responses of the participants. The researcher employed the 6-step thematic analysis process of

Braun and Clarke which starts with familiarization followed by coding, generating themes, reviewing the themes, defining, and naming the themes and finally writing up the analysis. The process investigated the participants' perception of the causal factors of mental health concerns; mental health services and program of their university; and the readiness of the university in implementing mental health programs to understand the phenomenon of even with mental health programs, policies and advocacy activities in place the mental health concerns are still a growing problem in universities.

To summarize, the researcher used a mixed methods approach to assess the level of awareness for mental health literacy. In the quantitative part, they used the Mental Health Literacy questionnaire (MHLq) to collect data on participants' knowledge and understanding of mental health. In the qualitative part, they conducted semi-structured focus group interviews to gather in-depth information about participants' perceptions of mental health.

Table 1. Shows the summary of the research process

Procedure	Samples	Questionnaire
Quantitative Part	N = 436	Mental Health Literacy Questionnaire
Qualitative Part	N = 50	Semi-structured Focus Group Interviews

Participants

The study was conducted in selected universities in Metro Manila. Respondents were composed of stakeholders who were randomly selected. The following factors were not included in the study gender, age, course, year level, educational background, or nationality.

For this research, there were a total of 442 participants with the following breakdown:

Table 2: Participants Category

Participants Category	Number of Respondents
Students	342
Faculty	48
Employees	44
Administrators	8

Table 2 shows the breakdown of the 442 participants with 342 students, 48 faculty, 44 employee, and 8 administrator participants.

Table 3. Profile of Participants per University Category

University Category	Name Of School	City	Number of Respondents
(Univ001) State Univerity	GU001	Manila	Student-27 Faculty-9 Employee-4 Administrator-1 Total=41
	GU002	Quezon City	Student-5 Faculty-1 Total=6
	GU003	Manila	Student-6 Faculty-2 Employee-2 Administrator-1 Total=11
	GU004	Manila	Student-2 Total=2
(Univ002)	PSU001	Manila	Student-85 Faculty-3 Employee-4 Administrator-1 Total=93
	PSU002	Manila	Employee-2 Total=2
	PSU003	Quezon City	Employee-1 Total=1
Private Sectarian	PSU004	Manila	Student-2 Total=2
	PSU005	Manila	Student-9 Faculty-4 Employee-3 Total=16
	PSU006	Manila	Administrator-1 Total=1

	PSU007	Las Pinas	Student-1 Faculty-1 Total=2
	PNSU001	Manila	Employee-1 Total=1
(Univ 003)		Caloocan	Student-2 Employee-1

Table 3 shows the summary of the profile breakdown of participants in each university category. The State University category was coded as a group as UNIV001 with 60 participants coming from 4 State universities located in Manila and Quezon City. Private Sectarian University was coded as Univ 002 with 117 participants coming from 7 private sectarian universities located in Manila, Quezon City, and Las Pinas. Private Non-Sectarian University was coded with Univ 003 with 265 participants coming from 4 private non-sectarian universities located in Manila and Caloocan.

Instruments

In this study, the Mental Health Literacy Questionnaire (MHLq) young adult form (Campos, et.al. 2018) was employed to assess the mental health literacy of the participants according to very high, high, mid, low and very low levels. Compared to other MHLq assessment tools, the young adult form provides a comprehensive approach to mental health literacy, covering a range of dimensions and disorders in a short amount of time. Mental health professionals and researchers may use this tool to screen for intervention needs and to design effective mental health programs. Identifying knowledge gaps and erroneous beliefs concerning mental health issues is essential in addressing the need for mental health literacy promotion (Campos, et.al. 2018).

This tool consists of 29 items grouped into four subscales, which include first aid skills and help-seeking skills, knowledge/stereotypes, erroneous beliefs/stereotypes, and self-help strategies. It is a valid and reliable assessment that can identify knowledge gaps, erroneous beliefs, and behavioral intentions, and can be used to design and evaluate mental health literacy promotion programs. Pilot testing and validation procedures were omitted in this particular research because the researcher obtained permission from the test developers to utilize the MHLq in the context of this specific study. The tool had previously undergone validation by its original author.

Using exploratory factor analysis and internal consistency analysis, the 29- item tool has reported internal consistency of Cronbach's α coefficients of 0.84. It has four dimensions (1) knowledge of mental health problems $\alpha = 0.74$; (2) erroneous beliefs/stereotypes $\alpha = 0.72$; (3) help-seeking and first aid skills $\alpha = 0.71$; and (4) self-help strategies $\alpha = 0.60$ (Diaz, et al. 2018).

An interview guide, sometimes known as an aide-memoire, was used in this study as a method of collecting qualitative data. The questions in this guide probed the participants' understanding of mental health, including their opinions on the factors that lead to mental diseases, the mental health services provided by their universities, and the existence of a school mental health program. Prior to using the aide-memoire in the focus group interview, three guidance counselors who are considered experts in the field were requested to validate it.

Procedure

The researcher began the study by obtaining permission from the authors/developers of the MHLq for its use in the research. Following approval, an aide memoire was crafted to assess participants' perceptions of mental health, the causes of mental illness, and the mental health services and programs offered by their respective universities. Three mental health experts validated the aide memoire.

Upon approval of the instruments and the research proposal, a request letter was submitted to the Office of Research of the selected universities. Once approval was granted, the administration of the MHLq and the focus group discussions/interviews with selected participants were scheduled online using Google Meet or Zoom platforms, in light of the Covid-19 pandemic. The MHLq was administered online via Google Forms, which was included in the validation process. On the day of administration, participants were introduced to the study, asked to sign the research consent forms, and fill out a profile sheet as part of the rapport-building process.

Quantitative Data Gathering. There were 442 participants with 342 students, 48 faculty, 44 employees, and 8 administrators who were administered MHLq. Before the participants answered the Mental Health Literacy Questionnaire (MHLq), they were briefed about the test's objective and the research. Moreover, they were offered psychological debriefing both before and after the test administration.

Qualitative Data Gathering. From the 442 participants, a total of 45 participants, with 25 students and 10 employees, 10 faculty, and 5 administrators, were selected to take part in a semi-structured focus group interview. The interview guide, which was validated by three mental health experts, was used during the interview process. Participants were provided with an overview of the interview's purpose and were offered to debrief before and after the interview. To maintain the confidentiality and anonymity of the participants, data were analyzed using coding. The interview was conducted online via Google Meet, with participants having the option to turn on or off their cameras. Although the study did not cause any direct harm, participants were offered debriefing at the conclusion of the interview because some questions may have elicited emotional distress.

Ethical Considerations

To uphold ethical standards and establish rapport, the participants were informed and provided with informed consent forms prior to the start of the study. The forms comprehensively explained the research's purpose, nature, procedures, goals, risks, background, and

benefits. The participants were also made aware of their involvement, right to withdraw, and the researcher's confidentiality limitations. Furthermore, the research objectives and data gathering procedures were disclosed. Following the questionnaire, participants were randomly selected and invited to attend a focus group discussion/interview, where they were again informed of the purpose of the interview. To ensure confidentiality, each interviewee was assigned a code. The interviews were conducted via Google Meet, and participants were given the option to open or close their cameras. Although the study did not cause direct harm to participants, some sensitive questions may have elicited undesirable emotions. Thus, participants were provided with a debriefing at the conclusion of the interview.

Results and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the findings of this study using tables and descriptive summaries gained through logical analysis, theme clustering, and validation of responses. The data would support future research and contribute to psychosocial education, mental health awareness programs, and mental health policies.

Quantitative Results

1. What is the prevailing level of mental health literacy of the different categories of participants in terms of:

- 1.1 knowledge about mental health problems;
- 1.2 erroneous beliefs/stereotypes;
- 1.3 first-aid skills and help-seeking behavior; and
- 1.4 self-help strategies?

The following is a summary table showing the computed mean average of the participant's level of mental health literacy as measured by the Mental Health Literacy questionnaire (MHLq).

Table 4. Summary of results of Level of Mental Health Literacy

Participants Category	Factor1		Factor2		Factor 3		Factor 4		Overall Level	
	$\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}$	SD
Students	46.60	5.09	32.16	3.56	24.16	3.75	24.16	3.75	120.70	10.14
	High		Low		High		High		Very High	
Faculty	45.88	5.54	31.90	3.46	26.07	2.97	26.07	2.97	121.86	11.21
	High		Low		Very High		Very High		Very High	
Employee	45.82	7.37	32.23	4.01	25.11	4.97	25.11	4.97	121.05	17.86
	High		Low		High		High		Very High	
Administrator	49.63	3.16	32.00	2.51	27.50	1.31	27.50	1.31	128.13	6.38
	Very High		Low		Very High		Very High		Very High	

Results show that participants in all categories rated high to very high in Factors 1,3, and 4 and low in Factor 2. Furthermore, they rated Very High in terms of the overall level of mental health literacy. Below shows a more detailed discussion of the results per factor. The following table shows their overall mental health literacy level. Comparing the group results of participants (students, faculty, employee, and administrators) per university category (State university, private sectarian university, private non-sectarian university):

Table 5. Summary of results of Overall Level of Mental Health Literacy per University Category

Participants Category	Univ 001 (State University Category)		Univ 002 (Private Sectarian University)		Univ 003 (Private Non-Sectarian University)	
	$\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}$	SD
Students	120.63	8.19	119.17	12.13	121.78	8.88
	High		High		High	
Faculty	120.75	14.93	119.00	13.42	123.71	9.18
	High		High		Very High	
Employee	112.83	39.47	126.90	7.19	120.71	13.20
	High		Very High		High	
Administrator	125.00	0.00	130.50	10.61	128.50	6.86
	Very High		Very High		Very High	

Results show that overall mental health literacy of student participants in all university categories (State university, private sectarian university, private non-sectarian university) rated high to very high while faculty participants in State universities and private sectarian universities rated high while faculty participants in private nonsectarian universities rated very high. Moreover, employee participants coming from State and private non-sectarian universities have high levels while those coming from private sectarian universities rated very high levels of mental health literacy. Furthermore, all administrator participants from all university categories were rated to have very high levels of mental health literacy. One reason why students, employees, faculty, and administrators all have high to very high levels of mental health literacy could be the implementation of various mental health awareness and training programs within the educational institution.

These programs may include initiatives such as workshops, seminars, and training sessions focused on raising awareness about mental

health, its importance, and various aspects related to it, such as common mental health disorders, signs and symptoms, available resources, and strategies for promoting mental well-being. By providing access to such educational opportunities, individuals in these roles can develop a deeper understanding and knowledge of mental health. They can gain insights into recognizing signs of distress, offering support, and promoting mental well-being both personally and with other people. The following discussion presents the participants levels in each factors namely: knowledge of mental health factors; erroneous beliefs or stereotypes; first aid skills and help-seeking behavior; and self-help strategies.

1.1 Factor 1 Knowledge of mental health problems

Factor 1 assessed the participants' knowledge of signs and symptoms of different mental health conditions as well as ways how to maintain healthy mental health.

Table 6. *Level of Mental Health Literacy in Factor 1 (Knowledge of mental health problems)*

<i>Participants Category</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Students	46.60	5.09	High
Faculty	45.88	5.54	High
Employee	45.82	7.37	High
Administrator	49.63	3.16	Very High

Table 6 shows the level of mental health literacy of the participants in terms of knowledge of mental health problems where the results indicate that the participants demonstrated a high level of knowledge regarding mental health problems. Specifically, administrators ranked highest with very high ratings, while student, faculty, and employee participants all ranked high.

This finding resulted to the participants have a comprehensive understanding of various mental health issues. Their strong knowledge in this area is crucial because it enables them to recognize the signs and symptoms of mental health problems, allowing for early intervention and support. Additionally, a high level of knowledge promotes accurate and empathetic attitudes toward mental health, reducing stigma and fostering a supportive environment.

The administrators' very high ratings are particularly significant as they play an important role in developing and implementing programs and policies related to mental health. Their extensive knowledge can contribute to the development of effective strategies and initiatives to support mental well-being within educational settings (Prizmah.org, 2020). Although the student, faculty, and employee participants ranked slightly lower than administrators, their high ratings still indicate an understanding of mental health problems. This suggests that they are equipped to recognize and respond to mental health concerns.

Many individuals, especially students, were becoming more aware of the issues of mental health thanks to several mental health awareness initiatives, particularly during the pandemic when there was an increase in the number of persons suffering from many mental health concerns. The majority of people who experienced mental health issues were mostly students.

This is supported by different studies (Slade, n.d.; Collier, 2019). Teenage years have a high number of people experiencing mental health concerns. Most teens this age is attending university which is considered to be one of the predominant factors of mental health issues including academic stress, peer pressure, bullying, and others. Collier (2019) mentioned in her article that three in four mental illnesses start in childhood. And people who work in schools are more likely to spend a lot of time with children who are struggling with mental health concerns. Furthermore, she emphasized the importance of having a school mental health policy to address the concerns. With the prevalence of mental health issues in school, numerous mental health awareness campaigns focused on providing knowledge about mental health problems. Since the topic is relevant to them, many youths participate in the advocacies and arm themselves with the knowledge needed (Collier, 2019; Brown, 2018; Weist et al., 2017; Engelhardt, 2016).

Meanwhile, faculty also rated high in this area. With the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, aside from students, the faculty and employees are among those who were affected. Career stability was suddenly shaken and there was an immediate shift in the mode of teaching and working. Work-related stress drastically increased along with physical stress, boredom, and health stress among other factors that contributed to the mental health concerns of many employees and faculty. They themselves are clamoring for a mental health program to help them with their mental wellbeing.

They mostly experienced mental health concerns like anxiety and depression (Handog, 2020). There were reports of teachers committing suicide and because of this the schools and universities need to act fast. Mental health awareness campaigns directed towards addressing their concerns were provided by some universities. However, the content, scope, and type of mental health service provided are not the same (standard) with all universities. Thus, there is a slight difference in the level of their knowledge of mental health. Brown (2018) made a review of the different published policies and information on the school's mental health and well-being provisions. She cited that there are only 13 primary schools and 14 secondary schools providing some form of universal support or preventive activities that promote mental health and well-being.

Moreover, employees also ranked high levels. With the detrimental effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the mental health of people, school-based mental health programs were implemented by DepEd, including psychosocial activities (Cruz, 2021). For the teaching and non-teaching personnel, they facilitated TAYO Naman!: Tulong, Yakap at Oras para sa mga Tagapagtaguyod ng Edukasyon which

was an online webinar that aimed to promote self-care during the pandemic (Malipot, 2021).

Administrators play a crucial role in the implementation of school programs including mental health activities. They should be knowledgeable and sympathetic to the people or school stakeholders experiencing mental health concerns. WHO (as mentioned by Sivaramakrishnan and Varnum, 2019) defined a healthy mental state as the state of well-being of a person realizing his or her own full potential, a person who can cope with the daily stresses of life, works productively and efficiently, and is able to make a contribution to her or his community.

With the Covid 19 pandemic and the fast-phasing life, daily life stressors are becoming more and more challenging and there is a growing trend in people experiencing mental health concerns. Sivaramakrishnan and Varnum (2019) call on a new type of leadership, a leader who shows strength by embracing vulnerability, exercising wisdom, and creating a psychologically safe space for their team. A leader who is innovative and open about mental health. It will be helpful and would make their team be more productive to work on their common goal. Anna Freud National Centre for Children and Families (n.d.) mentioned the importance of mental health and well-being of the school. It should be the core running through all school activities which links the priorities of the school. School leaders should be the forefront driving force in advocating mental health. They believed in the whole-school method in which all school stakeholders are committed to work together. There is a partnership between the administrators, parents, school staff, parents, and even the whole community.

1.2 Factor 2: Erroneous beliefs/stereotypes

Factor 2 assesses the participants' erroneous beliefs and stereotypical ideals regarding mental health conditions. Having low levels means that the participants have minimal wrong notions or beliefs regarding mental concerns.

Table 7. *Level of Mental Health Literacy in Factor 2 Erroneous beliefs/stereotypes*

<i>Participants Category</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Students	32.16	3.56	Low
Faculty	31.90	3.46	Low
Employee	32.23	4.01	Low
Administrator	32.00	2.51	Low

Table 7 shows the level of mental health literacy of the participants in terms of erroneous beliefs or stereotypes of mental health where all the participants rated low. By having low levels of erroneous beliefs or stereotypes, the participants demonstrate a more accurate and concrete understanding of mental health. This can have several positive implications such as reduced stigma, produces an empathic response, and enhanced well-being. Low levels of erroneous beliefs or stereotypes can contribute to improved overall well-being in educational or organizational settings. When individuals are knowledgeable about mental health, they can proactively address their own well-being and create an environment that prioritizes mental wellness.

Most people suffering from mental illness delay seeking help and treatment because of limited knowledge of their condition (Ines, 2019). The continued mental health awareness activities like seminars and/or webinars provided accurate information about mental health conditions. These initiatives help in decreasing the stereotypical attitude and stigma toward people with mental health conditions. World Health Organization mentioned stigma and discrimination towards people suffering from mental and behavioral disorders as one of the most important barriers that need to be overcome in the community (2001). Stigma includes behaviors of stereotyping, prejudice, and discrimination. It leads to feelings of shame, guilt, despair, sadness, isolation, secrecy, loneliness, exclusion, negative labels, and being treated differently from the rest of the community. Stigma worsens a person's mental health condition and leads to reluctance to seek or even accept help. Most of the time, even their families are affected by stigma which often leads to a lack of disclosure and support.

University students with mental health issues often find it challenging to get the proper support because of stigma. Martin's (2009) exploratory study underscored the difficulty of students with mental health issues. Their apprehension stemmed from the fear of stigma and being discriminated in school because of their condition. Because of this many students were not able to get help and just concealed their concerns.

Furthermore, self-stigma or personal stigmatizing attitudes posed as a barrier to seeking help. Eisenberg, et al (2009) reports that among the participants in their study, personal stigma was higher among male, younger Asian, religious, and those coming from poor families.

Lindow et al. (2020) report that students help-seeking behaviors, mental health literacy, and mental health stigma decreased after the YAM or Youth Aware of Mental Health program was implemented. YAM is a universal, school-based mental health promotion/suicide primary prevention intervention for adolescents aged 12-18 years old (Lindow et al., 2020).

Aside from students, the faculty were also reported to experience mental health concerns, especially during the onset of the pandemic, it is inevitable for some to experience compassion fatigue. CHED recognizes the toll of the pandemic on the mental health of both students and teachers. Aside from equipping the teachers with the necessary technological skills to shift to online learning, there were also programs intended to take care of their mental well-being. Then CHED chief Prospero de Vera stressed the importance of taking care of the mental health not only of the students but also of the faculty members as 'anxiety, stress, and depression can reduce the

capacity of the students and faculty members to adapt to the new normal (Handog, 2020).

Employees experienced various stressors that affected their mental health. Hamouche (2020) examined the impact of the Coronavirus COVID-19 outbreak on employees' mental health particularly looking at their stressors. Results showed that perception of safety, threat, and risk of being infected, infobesity or too much information versus lack of information, quarantine and confinement, stigma, social isolation, financial loss, and job factor are among the stressors of the participants of the study.

With the different adversities that the students are experiencing that affect their mental health, school administrators are in a main position to lead a systemic change that would help address the problem. Many students with mental health concerns experience great difficulty which may impact their learning ability. Skaar, Townsley, and Ross (2022) created a primer for developing and implementing universal screening and comprehensive systems to support the students' mental health. According to them, school administrators should have a high level of mental health literacy and establish steps for a system that would take care of the students' mental health.

Moreover, Arnold et al. (2020) found that among the schools that participated or adopted a trauma-informed mindfulness intervention called RAP (Relax, be Aware and Do a Personal Rating) Club. Results of their study showed that administrators who chose to adopt the program because they wanted to provide support for students affected by trauma and prevent them from engaging in unhealthy coping behaviors. Factors that contributed to their decision are lack of trauma-informed mental health programs, inadequate fundings, and the perceived benefits of the program.

1.3 Factor 3: First aid skills and help-seeking behavior

Factor 3 measures the participants' skills in providing psychological first aid and attitudes that may facilitate help-seeking behavior. First aid skills refer to the ability to provide immediate assistance or support to someone experiencing a

mental health crisis or distress. Help-seeking behavior, on the other hand, pertains to individuals actively seeking professional help or support when facing mental health challenges. Both of these aspects are important for early intervention and ensuring appropriate care for individuals in need.

Table 8. *Level of Mental Health Literacy in Factor 3: First aid skills and help-seeking behavior*

<i>Participants Category</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Students	24.16	3.75	High
Faculty	26.07	2.97	Very High
Employee	25.11	4.97	High
Administrator	27.50	1.31	Very High

Table 8 shows the level of mental health literacy of the participants in terms of first aid skills and help-seeking behavior. Results show that students and employees rated high while faculty and administrators resulted to have high levels.

The results showing high ratings in mental health literacy among students and employees indicate that these groups have a solid understanding of first aid skills and help-seeking behavior. This suggests that they are equipped to recognize signs of mental health distress and respond appropriately.

Furthermore, the very high levels among faculty and administrators are significant as their understanding of first aid skills and help-seeking behavior can play a major role in creating supportive environments within educational settings. Faculty members and administrators who are well-informed can develop policies, initiatives, and support systems that facilitate early intervention and encourage individuals to seek help when needed.

Overall, the high levels of mental health literacy in terms of first aid skills and help-seeking behavior among the participants indicate a positive outcome. It suggests that the participants, including students, employees, faculty, and administrators, possess the knowledge and skills necessary to provide immediate assistance and promote timely support for mental health concerns.

Many young people with mental health concerns experience difficulty seeking help. Pimenta (2020) mentions stigma, lack of trust in available resources, and severity of symptoms influence the help-seeking behavior of a person. However, it was also revealed that most of them open up regarding their concerns to people of the same age. The problem is they also do not know where or how to help or seek help to assist their peers. With this, she claims that knowing and understanding the different strategies to cope with psychological prove to be beneficial in helping and providing better mental health support to others.

This is a good sign especially while understanding the risk factors and reasons for mental health concerns is important, understanding the help-seeking behavior of young adults is also important. Mitchell, Mc Millan, and Hagan (2017) recognize this importance as early interventions may improve the prognosis of mental health concerns and reduce the severity and fast progression to co-morbid disorders.

1.4 Factor 4: Self-help strategies

Factor 4 measures the participants' attitudes that may facilitate helping themselves or their ability to engage in proactive and effective mental health management.

Self-help strategies refer to the practices and techniques individuals employ to promote their own mental well-being and cope with mental health challenges. Having a strong understanding of self-help strategies empowers individuals to take an active role in their mental health, promoting resilience, and reducing the impact of mental health issues.

Table 9. *Level of Mental Health Literacy in Factor 4: Self-help strategies*

<i>Participants Category</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Students	24.16	3.75	High
Faculty	26.07	2.97	Very High
Employee	25.11	4.97	High
Administrator	27.50	1.31	Very High

Table 9 shows the level of mental health literacy of the participants in terms of self-help strategies. Results showed that Faculty and Administrators rated very high levels of self-help strategies while students and employees got high levels as well.

The results imply that they are knowledgeable about various techniques which can contribute to maintaining mental well-being and managing symptoms of distress. Moreover, the high levels of mental health literacy among faculty and administrators are also significant as their understanding of self-help strategies enables them to model and promote these techniques within their environment. Faculty members and administrators who are well-versed in self-help strategies can guide and support students and employees in creating their own self-care routines, normalizing a culture of healthy mental well-being.

Having a good level of self-help strategies enables an individual to seek help as many young people who experience mental health concerns find it challenging to seek help. Pimenta (2020) suggests that stigma, lack of trust in available resources, and the severity of symptoms influence an individual's help-seeking behavior. However, most of these individuals tend to open up to peers of their age group. The problem is that they may not know how or where to seek help for their peers. Understanding and being aware of the different strategies for coping with psychological issues can be beneficial in providing better mental health support to others.

Self-stigma refers to the negative self-labeling that an individual may adopt regarding their own capabilities to interact with society. Research has shown that self-stigma has a detrimental effect on an individual's self-worth, self-esteem, and can even exacerbate mental health conditions (Corrigan et al., 2006; Holmes & River, 1998; Link & Phelan, 2001, as cited by Pheko et al., 2013). Upon receiving a mental illness diagnosis, an individual may internalize cultural stereotypes and ideas about mental illness, resulting in negative feelings towards themselves and an anticipation of rejection and mockery from others. These feelings may trigger defensive behaviors such as hiding their diagnosis and treatment history, withdrawing from social situations, and decreasing their mental health awareness (Pheko et al., 2013). In their study, Pheko et al. (2013) hypothesized that self-stigmatization would lead to (1) low intentions of seeking professional psychological help, (2) diminished positive attitudes towards seeking professional psychological help, (3) a negative association between the stigma of receiving psychological help and intentions of seeking professional psychological help, and (4) self-stigma of seeking psychological help would negatively predict intentions of seeking professional psychological help.

While understanding the risk factors and reasons for mental health concerns is essential, understanding the help-seeking behavior of young adults is also crucial. Mitchell, Mc Millan, and Hagan (2017) recognize this importance as early interventions may improve the prognosis of mental health concerns and reduce the severity and fast progression to co-morbid disorders. Goodwin, Behan, Kelly, Mc Carthy, and Horgan (2016) conducted a study at a university and found that despite experiencing low levels of mental well-being, students exhibited poor help-seeking behaviors. Furthermore, they preferred to informally seek help from their friends rather than mental health professionals. Their findings also emphasize the importance of mental health awareness as this can improve the help-seeking behaviors of young people.

This was supported by Reachout (n.d.), an online support group that mentions different reasons preventing a person from seeking help. Aside from the fear of stigma and embarrassment, most people would resort to self-reliance that to seek help. Others fear that their confidentiality might be violated and have trust issues. They may also experience feelings of hopelessness. Moreover, they shared the effective facilitators of enhancing or increasing the help-seeking behaviors of young adults. Having positive previous experiences may help them to seek help again. Invalidation and stigma should be avoided and social support and encouragement from others will help. They will also gain emotional confidence by having a high level of mental health literacy.

Having high level of mental health literacy is essential in the delivery of mental health services as it promotes early recognition of symptoms, reduces stigma, encourages help-seeking behavior, improves treatment adherence, empowers self-care, enhances communication and support, and facilitates prevention and early intervention. By equipping individuals with knowledge and understanding, mental health literacy contributes to a more informed and supportive approach to mental health care.

2. Is there a significant difference in the level of mental health literacy of the participants?

To identify the appropriate statistical treatment to test the significant difference in the level of mental health literacy of participants, the test of normality using Kolmogorov-Smirnov was applied to the quantitative data gathered.

Table 10. *Kolmogorov-Smirnov test of normality results*

Category	Statistic	df	Sig.	Decision
Students	.064	342	.002	Not significant
Employee	.204	44	<.001	Not significant
Administrators	.313	8	.020	Not significant
Faculty	.123	48	.109	Not significant

Table 10 shows the computation of the test of normality utilizing Kolmogorov-Smirnov. Using the SPSS, the p-value derived is less than 0.05 therefore it is concluded that the samples came from different distributions.

Having concluded that the distribution of the data is not equally distributed, the researcher used the Kruskal-Wallis Test to measure the significant difference in the level of mental health literacy between students, faculty, employee and administrators.

Kruskal -Wallis is a non-parametric test used for variables with unequal distribution. The table below shows the Kruskal-Wallis computation with a 0.05 level of significance using SPSS.

Table 11. *Kruskal-Wallis Computation of the significant difference in the overall Mental Health Literacy of the Participants*

Test Statistics	
	Score
Kruskal-Wallis H	7.209
Df	3
Asymp Sig.	.006

Ranks		
Participant Category	N	Mean Rank
Students	342	211.62
Employee	44	245.49
Administrators	8	305.69
Faculty	48	229.68
Total	442	

Based on the results of the Kruskal-Wallis H test, the analysis indicates a failure to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that there was no statistically significant difference in the level of mental health literacy among students, faculty, employees, and administrators ($\chi^2(3) = 7.209$, $p = 0.066$). The mean rank mental health literacy scores were 211.62 for students, 245.49 for employees, 305.69 for administrators, and 229.68 for faculty.

The finding implies that the efforts aimed at promoting mental health awareness have been successful among students, faculty, employees, and administrators. It signifies a positive step towards addressing mental health challenges in the educational setting.

To ensure the continued impact and sustainability of these initiatives, the development of a comprehensive school mental health policy is crucial. Without a guiding policy, the momentum and effectiveness of the activities may diminish over time. A well-structured policy provides a framework for ongoing support, resources, and strategies to address mental health needs. It helps maintain a consistent and proactive approach to mental health promotion, intervention, and support within the educational institution.

By implementing a school mental health policy, educational institutions can create a supportive and inclusive environment that prioritizes mental well-being. The policy can outline clear guidelines and protocols for early identification of mental health issues, access to resources and services, and collaboration among stakeholders. It also helps foster a culture that values and prioritizes mental health, reducing stigma and promoting help-seeking behaviors.

While the finding demonstrates the effectiveness of mental health awareness efforts in the educational setting, it highlights the importance of developing a school mental health policy. Such a policy ensures the consistency, longevity, and impact of these initiatives, providing a comprehensive framework for addressing mental health challenges and promoting a supportive environment for all individuals involved.

With the Covid 19 pandemic the whole world is experiencing, there is a rise in mental health crises among many people. One of the effects of the pandemic includes lower levels of mental health. Fear of the illness (Covid19), isolation because of being in quarantine for a long time, change in way of living as we needed to use technology in everything, and cabin fever are some of the effects of the pandemic. With these, various agencies are proactive in providing mental health awareness, especially in schools. Private or State schools all have mental health awareness campaigns. Local studies showed that students who exhibited mental health concerns reported having relational problems with their parents and/or their peers, financial concerns, and/or academic pressures (Lee, et.al, 2013; Go-Monilla, 2015). With this in mind, it is therefore the schools' duty to formulate an effective school mental health program to help the students cope with their concerns.

Qualitative Results

Exploring the personal experiences of individuals affected by mental health concerns can shed light on the intricacies of the conditions and provide valuable insights about mental well-being.

The responses reflect the participants' experiences with people who are experiencing mental health problems. Mental health is a complex and subjective topic that encompasses individual experiences, perceptions, and emotions. Focus group discussion allowed the participants to express their thoughts and feelings in their own words. This captured the lived experiences and distinctions of mental health literacy.

3. How do the factors identified as causes of mental health problems connect to the results of mental health literacy?

Understanding the relationship between the factors identified as causes of mental health problems and the results of mental health literacy can illuminate the connections and implications for promoting awareness and effective interventions in mental health care.

It was discovered that only a few respondents personally knew someone who had been clinically diagnosed with a mental health disorder, although, some of the respondents themselves had been clinically diagnosed. The range of mental health concerns mentioned by the participants included depression, anxiety, and bipolar disorder, as well as milder manifestations such as stress-related issues.

A deeper analysis of the participants' responses yielded the following themes as the respondents perceived causal factors of mental health concerns:

Table 12. *Thematic analysis of the perceived causal factors of mental health concerns*

Main Theme	Sub-Themes	Salient Responses
Anxiety Provoking Thoughts	Trauma	"My fears resurface..." "bumabalik yung mga takot ko..."
		"When Daddy raises his voice, I tremble even if I'm not the one being scolded." "Pag napapasigaw si Daddy, nanginginig po ako kahit hindi ako yung pinagagalitan"
		"Just the sound of Daddy's voice getting louder, even if he's not angry, scares me, and I suddenly start crying." "Basta lumakas boses ni Daddy kahit di siya galit, natatakot ako, naiiyak ako bigla" "I wake up at night with so many thoughts running through my mind." "Nagigising ako sa gabi ang daming tumatakbo sa isip ko."
	Overthinking	"One bad thought leads to another and another and another... It's a never-ending cycle." "One bad thought leads to another and another and another.... Never ending cycle"
		"It's difficult to control once I start thinking. Sometimes, I can't stop my emotions, and I end up crying uncontrollably." "Ang hirap po kontrolin once nagstart na ako mag-isip." "Minsan di ko na din mapigil pati emosyon ko iyak ako ng iyak."
		"The pandemic shook me to the core. Many people got sick and died." "Pandemic shook my core. Maraming nagkasakit at namatay."
Covid19 Induced Anxiety	"I was scared to leave the house... scared of losing my job." "Natakot ako lumabas ng bahay... mawalan ng trabaho"	
	"If someone sneezes or coughs beside me, I get nervous. It's stressful to go out of the house, and when I return, I feel like I have a fever." "May bumahing o umubo sa tabi ko ninenerbyos na ako. Nakakastress lumabas ng bahay, paguwi ko feeling ko may lagnat na ako." "Lalo akong pumangit at tumaba nung pandemic."	
Poor Self-Concept	"Yung thoughts ko po ay bakit yung iba nag glow up habang pandemic ako ito pangit pa rin."	
		"Lumalayo po si ate parang nagwithdraw pati sa amin di nakikipagusap. Sabi niya lagi okay lang siya magisa kaysa makaistorbo sa amin"

		"As far as I know, that kind of thing can be inherited..." "Ang alam ko po namamana yung ganun..."
Biological Factors	Heredity/ Genetics	"I know someone who might have inherited it because their father is also like that." "Yung kakilala ko, namana nya yata kasi Papa nya ganun din."
		"They say it's all in my head." "Sinasabi nila nasa isip ko lang daw po ito."
		"I've been diagnosed, but my mother says I just lack prayer." "Maam diagnosed po ako pero sabi ni Mama kulang ako sa dasal."
Anxiety Provoking Situations	Lack Of Support of Family and/or Friends	"When I share my problems with my friends, it feels like we're in a competition... and their problems always seem worse. That's why I don't tell them anymore. My moment becomes their moment." "Pag nagkwento ako sa friends ko para kaming may contest... mas malala ang problema siya winner. Kaya di na ako nagsasabi. Moment ko nagiging moment nila."
Anxiety Provoking Situations		"They have high expectations of me. I'm really struggling." "Ang taas ng expectation nila sa akin. Hirap na hirap na ako"
	Pressure	"Sometimes, I force myself to push harder, thinking my efforts are still insufficient." "Minsan pinipilit ko ipush sarili ko na kulang pa mga efforts ko."
		"I've seen it in movies... being bullied and then getting depressed." "Nakikita ko po like sa movies.... binully tapos nadedepress"
	Bullying	"I'm targeted at the office. There's always something to criticize about me." "Pinag-iinitan ako sa office. Laging may pinupuna sa akin."
		"Sometimes... it's inevitable, I get affected by what I watch. It's like something relatable but not quite, yet I still feel sad." "Minsan po.... Di maiwasan, naapektuhan ako ng napapanood ko. Ahm yung parang relatable na hindi pero feel ko nasasad din ako."
	Social Media Driven Anxiety	"I read somewhere that people tend to imitate or be affected by what they see or hear when a well-known person commits suicide." "May nabasa po ako, yung parang nagagaya nila pag may napanood or nabalitaan na may nagsuicide na kilalang tao."
Lifestyle Stressors		"The online classes are really challenging, Ma'am. I can't handle the amount of requirements." "Grabe po ang online classes Ma'am. Di ko kinakaya ang dami ng requirements."
	Academic Stress	"Just when one deadline is given, another one is immediately set for the next day." "Kakabigay lang deadline agad kinabukasan"
	Academic Stress	"After one subject is posted, two or three more assignments are given right away." "Pagpost ng isang subject, dalawa o tatlo agad ang papagawa"
Lifestyle Stressors		

	<p>"It's really difficult to adjust to shifting to online mode because of the limited space at home." <i>"Shifting to online mode napakahirap magadjust kasi maliit space sa bahay."</i></p>
Work Related Stress	<p>"My boss is always monitoring me. They might as well install CCTV on me." <i>"Yung boss ko laging nakabantay. Kabitan nya na lang kaya ako ng CCTV"</i></p> <p>"Transitioning to online mode adds to the expenses." <i>"Dagdag gastos yung pagonline"</i></p> <p>"Many of my co-workers lost their jobs, got laid off, so I really need to put in extra effort in my work to avoid being let go." <i>"Madami akong katrabaho na nawalan ng work, natanggal kaya sobrang need ko ieffort ang pagwork para di matsugi."</i> <i>"I have so many loans, and I can't sleep because I keep thinking about them." "Dami kong loans, di na ako makatulog kakaisip."</i></p>
Financial Stress	<p>"Sometimes, I think that if I die, all my debts will be gone... can debts be passed on?" <i>"Minsan naiisip ko pag namatay ako tapos na lahat ng utang ko.... napapasa ba ang utang?"</i></p>
Little Knowledge on Mental Health	<p>"It's unavoidable to with them, then they will talk about my condition." <i>"Di maiwasan sumabay kumain, tapos pagkkwentuhan nila ang condition ko."</i></p> <p>"They label me and say things like 'that person is depressed because she is weak.' <i>"Nilalabel sasabihan. like 'yan depress yan mahina kasi eh"</i></p>
Stigma And Discrimination	<p>"With friends, it feels like I have a disease; sometimes, they avoid talking to me. They can be toxic." <i>"Sa friends, para akong may sakit, iniwasan nila ako minsan kausapin. Natotoxic sila."</i></p> <p>"Sometimes I hear people saying, 'That person is crazy.' <i>"Minsan narinig ko sabi 'baliw na yan'"</i></p>
Little Knowledge on Mental Health	<p>"I want to accompany her for a check-up, but I don't know where, to whom, or how." <i>"Gusto ko siya samahan magpacheck up kaso di ko po alam saan at kanino o paano."</i></p>
Help Seeking Knowledge	<p>"In our barangay, there was a person who had a breakdown, they said there was a problem with his mental state. It took a long time for them to get help because no one knew what to do." <i>"Sa barangay po namin, may itinawag na nagwawala, sabi may problema sa pagiisip. Matagal natulungan kasi di rin nila alam gagawin nila."</i></p> <p>"She keeps crying, and I tried to comfort her, but I don't know if what I'm doing or saying was right." <i>"Iyak siya ng iyak, kinocomfort ko naman po kaso di ko alam kung tama ginagawa or sinasabi ko."</i></p> <p>"I ended up crying too because I feel sorry for her, and I'm scared she might commit suicide." <i>"Naiyak na lang din ako kasi naawa ako saka natatakot kasi baka magpakamatay siya"</i></p>

understanding the subjective experiences and the meaning attached by the respondent to their lived experiences as narrated during the interview (Figgou & Pavlopoulos, 2015). There were five main themes that were identified based on the participants' responses namely: Anxiety Provoking Thoughts (with subthemes: Trauma, Overthinking, Covid-19 Induced Anxiety, and Poor self-concept); Biological Factors (with subthemes Heredity/Genetics); Anxiety Provoking Situations (with subthemes Lack of support from the family and/or friends, Pressure, Bullying, Social Media Driven Anxiety); Lifestyle Stressors (with subthemes Academic Stress, Work Related Stress, Financial Stress); Little Knowledge On Mental Health (with subthemes Stigma and discrimination, Help-seeking knowledge)

Anxiety Provoking Thoughts (with subthemes: Trauma, Overthinking, Covid-19 Induced Anxiety, and Poor self-concept) were among the effects of the Covid 19 pandemic. Participants described past traumatic experiences as contributing to their mental health concerns, potentially impacting their well-being while some participants mentioned excessive rumination or obsessive thoughts as sources of anxiety and distress. Additionally, the ongoing pandemic was identified as a significant factor causing heightened anxiety and uncertainty. Many studies on the effect of the Covid 19 pandemic on mental health revealed that there was an increase in those who experienced moderate to severe levels of anxiety (Tee et al., 2020; Macgoron, 2023; Baclig, 2022; Dumalaon & Canaria 2021, Omengan, nd.). Poor self-concept and heredity may also affect the mental health of a person (Abtahi and Valladao, 2022, Busch et al., 2021).

Another causal factor was Anxiety Provoking Situations (with subthemes Lack of support from the family and/or friends, Pressure, Bullying, Social Media Driven Anxiety). Participants shared that a lack of emotional support or strained relationships as sources of anxiety. Furthermore, academic, professional, or societal expectations were cited as anxiety-inducing factors. Some shared of bullying, which adversely affected their mental well-being. Moreover, the influence of social media and its potential role in triggering anxiety and self-comparison was acknowledged.

The result was supported by different studies (Kentucky et al. Care, n.d.; Mace, 2020, Gaspar et al., 2020, Chang et al., 2021). They all mentioned the social and interpersonal factors contributing to the deterioration of the mental health of a person. Another factor is Biological Factors (with a subtheme of Heredity and Genetics). Participants acknowledged the role of genetics or family history in their susceptibility to mental health concerns.

Lifestyle Stressors (with subthemes of Academic Stress, Work Related Stress, and Financial Stress) are also among the biggest contributor to mental health problems. Participants mentioned the pressures associated with academic performance and the impact it had on their mental health. Working participants highlighted stressors originating from work environments, such as excessive workload or toxic dynamics. Additionally, financial stress; economic instability, and financial difficulties were identified as significant stressors impacting mental health. Zaman, Hankir, and Jemni (2019) mentioned that lifestyle plays an important role (positive or negative) in the mental health of a person. While stress is an inevitable part of life proper coping or management is a life skill. During the onset of the pandemic and people are required to quarantine or be inside their homes because of lockdown many people felt the negative effects of stress. Jagoo (2021) mentioned that lifestyle has some effects on the mental health of many people. Savage (2020) added that the negative effects of stress caused by the pandemic could have long-lasting effects on people. Moreover, Hoffower and Akhtar (2020) longer work hours contributed to the mental health deterioration of many millennials.

The last theme derived from the FGD was Little Knowledge on Mental Health (with a subtheme of Stigma and discrimination, Help-seeking knowledge). Participants noted societal stigma and discrimination as barriers to seeking help and discussing mental health openly. Moreover, some participants expressed limited awareness or knowledge regarding available mental health resources and support services.

Even with many advocacies for mental health, the perceived causal factors of mental health concerns were described to be in contrast with the results of mental health literacy which resulted in high levels. Derived themes Anxiety Provoking Thoughts (with subthemes: Trauma, Overthinking, Covid-19 Induced Anxiety, and Poor self-concept); Biological Factors (with subthemes Heredity/Genetics); Anxiety Provoking Situations (with subthemes Lack of support from the family and/or friends, Pressure, Bullying, Social Media Driven Anxiety); Lifestyle Stressors (with subthemes Academic Stress, Work Related Stress, Financial Stress); Little Knowledge On Mental Health (with subthemes Stigma and discrimination, Help-seeking knowledge) showed contrasting characteristics from the high level of the mental health literacy factors which are knowledge of mental health problems; erroneous beliefs or stereotypes; first aid skills and help-seeking behavior; and self-help strategies.

The contrasting characteristics between these themes and the high levels of mental health literacy factors indicate a complex landscape. While the participants exhibited high levels of knowledge regarding mental health problems, erroneous beliefs or stereotypes, first aid skills and help-seeking behavior, and self-help strategies, the perceived causal factors highlighted various personal and contextual factors that contribute to mental health concerns.

These findings suggest that even with a high level of mental health literacy, individuals may still face challenges arising from personal experiences, societal pressures, and limited support systems. The presence of these contrasting characteristics calls for a comprehensive approach that combines knowledge-based interventions with addressing the underlying causes of mental health concerns. Efforts should focus on reducing stigma, improving support networks, addressing systemic stressors, and promoting resilience-building strategies to foster holistic mental well-being.

Knowledge of mental health problems, Erroneous beliefs/stereotypes

Despite rating high on knowledge of mental health problems and low in erroneous beliefs or stereotypes, the participants shared the following reasons such as past trauma, irrational fears, academic and work-related stressors, pressure, lack of support from loved ones, bullying, stigma, frustration, unhealthy relationships, environmental factors, genetics or heredity, social media, family problems, poor self-concept, overthinking, and the pandemic.

Mental health is affected by numerous factors that can lead to dysfunctionality or problems. Biological factors such as genetics or heredity, imbalances in brain chemicals, and life experiences such as trauma or abuse are some examples. According to Erskine (2014), about 23% of years lost because of disability can be attributed to mental and substance use disorders.

The shared causal factors characterized poor knowledge and stigma in relation to mental health concerns. Recent studies have indicated that students with mental health concerns frequently report relational problems with their parents and peers, financial concerns, and academic pressure as significant stressors in their lives (Lee et al., 2013; Go-

Monilla, 2015). Given these findings, it is crucial for schools to develop effective mental health programs to assist students in coping with their concerns. By addressing the multifaceted causes of mental illness, such programs can help to promote positive mental health outcomes and reduce the negative impact of mental illness on students' academic and personal lives. One of the ill effects of mental health concerns is stigma. Stigma is a pervasive social problem that has far-reaching consequences for individuals with mental and behavioral disorders. It can be defined as a mark of shame or discredit, and it is often characterized by behaviors such as stereotyping, prejudice, and discrimination. The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified stigma and discrimination as major barriers to effective mental health care in the community (WHO, 2001).

Aside from receiving stigma from other people, the prevalence of self-stigma should also be addressed. Self-stigma refers to the negative self-labeling that an individual may adopt regarding their own capabilities to interact with society. Research has shown that self-stigma has a detrimental effect on an individual's self-worth, and self-esteem, and can even exacerbate mental health conditions (Corrigan et al., 2006; Holmes & River, 1998; Link & Phelan, 2001, as cited by Pheko et al., 2013).

To address the issue of stigma, it is important to raise awareness and education about mental health concerns in the community. This can involve public campaigns and initiatives aimed at challenging negative attitudes and stereotypes. It is also important to provide support and resources to individuals and families affected by mental health conditions. This can include counseling, therapy, and other forms of mental health treatment, as well as peer support and community-based programs. By diminishing the stigma and encouraging acceptance and understanding, we can create a more inclusive and sympathetic environment for individuals with mental health concerns.

First Aid skills, Help-seeking behavior, Self-help strategies

First-hand experience with mental health issues, either personally or through someone close, makes the issue more relatable and drives people to research and learn more about the condition. Goodwin et al. (2016) found that despite experiencing low levels of mental well-being, students tend to exhibit poor help-seeking behaviors and prefer to seek help informally from friends rather than mental health professionals. This highlights the importance of mental health awareness, which can improve young people's help-seeking behaviors.

Riggio (2015) identified five key signs that may indicate an individual is experiencing distress and may require assistance, including changes in personality, persistent and uncharacteristic anxiety, anger, or moodiness, social withdrawal, self-neglect or engagement in risky behaviors, and overwhelming feelings of hopelessness. It is highly recommended that individuals experiencing these symptoms seek help, and it is important for others to offer support to those who may be exhibiting these signs (Riggio, 2015).

Aside from the fear of stigma and embarrassment, most people would resort to self-reliance to seek help. Others fear that their confidentiality might be violated and have trust issues. They may also experience feelings of hopelessness (Reachout, n.d.). Moreover, they shared the effective facilitators for enhancing or increasing the help-seeking behaviors of young adults. Having positive previous experiences may help them to seek help again. Invalidation and stigma should be avoided and social support and encouragement from others will help. They will also gain emotional confidence by having a high level of mental health literacy.

Understanding the help-seeking behavior of the youth is a crucial aspect in addressing mental health concerns as it may lead to early interventions, improved prognosis, and reduced severity of co-morbid disorders (Mitchell, Mc Millan, & Hagan, 2017). Goodwin et al. (2016) conducted a study at a university and found that despite experiencing low levels of mental well-being, students exhibited poor help-seeking behaviors. They preferred to seek help informally from their peers rather than from mental health professionals. This highlights the importance of mental health awareness as it can improve the help-seeking behaviors of young people. Therefore, it is essential to not only identify the risk factors and reasons for mental health concerns but also to promote mental health awareness and encourage young adults to seek professional help when needed.

Although the Mental Health Literacy questionnaire yielded high levels of mental health literacy among the participants, specifically on knowledge of mental health problems, first aid skills and help-seeking behavior, and self-help strategies, and low levels of erroneous

beliefs or stereotypes, the findings may not accurately reflect the experiences of the participants during the interview. Despite their high scores on the questionnaire, some respondents reported experiencing stigma and hearing discriminatory remarks from others, indicating a discrepancy between their knowledge and actual experiences related to mental health concerns. Moreover, some respondents expressed willingness to help but lacked the knowledge and skills to seek help or refer others to appropriate mental health professionals. It is worth noting that the questionnaire may have limitations in thoroughly assessing the mental health literacy of the participants in relation to their experiences with mental health concerns.

These findings underscore the need for universities to develop a more comprehensive mental health program that addresses not only the cognitive aspects of mental health literacy but also the experiential and psychosocial aspects of mental health. Universities can play a vital role in addressing the stigma surrounding mental health issues and promoting an atmosphere of acceptance and support by nurturing a supportive school environment that recognizes the prevalence of mental health concerns and encourages genuine and non-judgmental communication. Additionally, providing university stakeholders with the necessary knowledge and skills to seek and provide help for mental health concerns can help universities meet the needs of their stakeholders and enhance their well-being.

4. How does the level of mental health literacy impact the delivery of mental health services available in universities?

The participants shared that universities from Univ 001 or universities categorized as State University, offer mental health awareness activities such as in the form of seminars/webinars and training, counseling, and psychological testing.

The participants shared that universities from Univ 002 or universities categorized as Private Sectarian Universities, also offer mental health awareness activities such as in the form of seminars/webinars and training, counseling, referrals to allied mental health professionals, and psychological testing. A unique mental health service for them is having in-house psychologists who helps in addressing the mental health concerns of the students.

Moreover, the participants shared that universities from Univ 003 or universities categorized as Private Nonsectarian University, also offer mental health awareness activities such as in the form of seminars/webinars and training, counseling, referrals to allied mental health professionals, and psychological testing. Unique services for them are providing trainings on psychological first aid to both students and employees.

The majority of participants emphasized the significance of possessing a strong foundation in mental health literacy for the effective delivery of mental health services. They expressed the belief that high levels of mental health literacy contribute to several positive outcomes, including early symptom recognition, reduced stigma, increased help-seeking behavior, improved treatment adherence, empowered self-care, enhanced communication and support, as well as facilitating prevention and early intervention efforts. Participants highlighted that equipping individual with knowledge and understanding of mental health plays a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness of programs and service delivery in this field.

With poor mental health literacy people diagnosed with mental health concerns may initially prefer to seek help from non-medical practitioners like faith healers, as noted by Pradhan (2014). This preference could stem from the stigma associated with mental illness, the availability and accessibility of non- medical services, and the belief that mental illnesses can only be cured by supernatural forces.

The Covid-19 pandemic and the fast-paced life have made daily life stressors increasingly challenging, resulting in a growing trend of mental health concerns. Sivaramakrishnan and Varnum (2019) advocate for a new type of leadership that embraces vulnerability, exercises wisdom, and creates psychologically safe spaces for teams. This type of leader is innovative and open about mental health. In England, schools provide various mental health promotion activities, such as teacher training, mental health interventions, and in-school counseling programs like the "Link program."

In the study of Ines (2018), respondents in her study suggested counselors, family, friends, psychologist, and psychiatrist as helpful to a person suffering from depression. Moreover, she found out that most college students mentioned counseling to be the most helpful strategy or intervention for a depressed individual. Considering the importance of mental health, there is a pressing need for the effective implementation and expanded scope of mental health services.

5. What suggestions were shared to improve the mental health programs or services?

Participants affiliated with State Universities or Univ001 expressed the need for additional resources, including increased manpower and budget allocation, to enhance the provision of mental health services. They emphasized the importance of continuous program implementation and urged for wider accessibility, highlighting the need to extend program availability to all school stakeholders who may have been unable to attend due to work commitments. Students specifically called for the expansion of mental health services to meet the growing demand and cater to the diverse needs of the student population.

Participants affiliated with Private Sectarian Universities or Univ002, particularly students, emphasized the importance of maintaining continuous program implementation beyond the pandemic period. They called for ongoing efforts to prioritize mental health, emphasizing that these programs should not be limited to crisis situations but rather integrated into the long-term educational framework.

Additionally, participants expressed a desire for a cultural shift within the university community, urging school stakeholders,

particularly faculty members, to not only acquire mental health knowledge but also demonstrate compassion and empathy towards students. They emphasized the need for faculty members to embody mental health literacy by actively supporting and understanding the challenges faced by students.

Participants affiliated with Private Nonsectarian Universities or Univ 003 voiced their support for sustainable mental health programs and emphasized the importance of establishing stronger partnerships with mental health facilities. They highlighted the need for robust referral systems to effectively assist students who require specialized mental health services.

Furthermore, participants recommended wider information dissemination about mental health programs to ensure that all members of the university community are aware of the available resources and support. They suggested implementing measures, such as mandating 100% attendance, as some faculty members may choose not to attend these activities. The participants recognized that those who refrain from attending such events are often the ones who would benefit the most from gaining additional mental health knowledge and awareness.

Considering the research gap of having a high level of mental health literacy but still having prevalent mental health concerns the table below shows the thematic analysis on the suggestions shared by the participants to improve the mental health programs or services in universities:

Thematic analysis of the suggestions to improve the implementation of mental health programs and services

Main Theme	Sub-Themes	Salient Responses
Sustainability	Continuous and consistent delivery of services	"There were a lot of mental health webinars during the pandemic. I wonder how it will be in the future?" "Dumami ang mental health webinars nung pandemic. Paano kaya sa susunod?"
		"We are only given tests." "Testing lang po ang binibigay sa amin"
	Additional Mental Health Services	"It would be great if the programs continue consistently, rather than just being provided when something happens." "Continues sana wag yung pag may nangyayari lang saka may program"
		lang kulang na kulang sa tao"
Alignment With Mental Health Law	Resources People involved Budget	"It takes a long time for the budget to be approved, so sometimes we have to find our own resources." " Tagal magpaapprove ng budget minsan sariling labas na naming"
		"We have a limited number of Registered Guidance Counselors (RGC), so we need to invite speakers for training, but it becomes a budget constraint. I hope we can have an increase in the number of guidance counselors." "Konti ang RGC, kailangan pa naming maginvite ng speaker to train. Kaso sa budget." "Sana madagdagan ang guidance counselor naming."
	Linkage with psychologists or psychiatrist	"Other departments such as NSTP, HRD, and the student council assist in the advocacy for mental health awareness." "Yung ibang department like NSTP at HRD at student council, they assist in the mental health awareness advocacies" "It's difficult to schedule an appointment with a psychiatrist, especially through charity programs." "Ang hirap magpashedule sa psychiatrist pag sa charity" "The cost of medication is expensive." "Ang mahal ng gamot"
Linkages	Linkage with hospitals	"Sometimes, we also don't know where to refer them." "Minsan di rin naming alam saan sila irerefer"
	Linkage with other mental health professionals	"I want to accompany them for a check-up, but I don't know where." "Gusto ko siya samahan magpatingin pero saan?"
	Free consultation and/or treatment	"They are not included in our benefits." "Di siya part ng benefits naming"

The table showed the themes derived from the verbalized suggestions to improve the implementation of mental health programs and

services. The participants suggested the themes Sustainability (with subthemes of continuous and consistent delivery of services and additional mental health services);

Improve The Facilitation (with subthemes of effective and efficient programs); Alignment With Mental Health Law (with subthemes of resources, people involved, and budget); Linkages (with subthemes of Linkage with psychologists or psychiatrist, Linkage with hospitals, Linkage with other mental health professionals, Free consultation and/or treatment).

The analysis of the participants' suggestions for improving the implementation of mental health programs and services reveals several key themes.

The theme of sustainability emerged, with participants emphasizing the importance of continuous and consistent delivery of services. They advocated for mental health programs that extend beyond crisis periods, ensuring ongoing support for individuals in need. Additionally, participants called for the expansion of available mental health services to cater to the diverse needs of the community.

The second theme focused on improving facilitation. Participants highlighted the need for effective and efficient programs that are evidence-based and well-designed. They emphasized the importance of delivering programs in a manner that maximizes their impact and benefits for individuals seeking mental health support.

The alignment with mental health law emerged as another significant theme. Participants identified the allocation of resources as crucial, including staffing, facilities, and equipment, to ensure the effective implementation of mental health programs and services. Additionally, they emphasized the importance of having well-trained mental health professionals and support staff to provide quality care and support. Adequate budget allocation was also recognized as vital for sustaining and expanding mental health initiatives.

Finally, participants emphasized the importance of linkages within the mental health ecosystem. They suggested establishing connections with psychologists, psychiatrists, hospitals, and other mental health professionals. These linkages would facilitate seamless referral, collaboration, and access to specialized care when needed. Furthermore, participants recommended providing free or affordable consultation and treatment options, ensuring that financial barriers do not hinder individuals from accessing mental health services.

The suggestions from participants reflect a comprehensive approach to improving mental health programs and services. By focusing on sustainability, effective facilitation, alignment with mental health laws, and establishing linkages, it is possible to enhance the accessibility, quality, and continuity of mental health support for individuals in need.

The well-being of students' mental health is closely linked to their school environment, which serves as their second home. Personal or other problems they encounter may have a significant impact on their academic performance. In a meta-analysis conducted by Engelhardt (2016), the author examined the vital roles schools play in supporting students' mental health, such as promoting activities that address the stigma surrounding mental health concerns, implementing intervention programs that equip students with coping strategies, and providing appropriate training to school personnel. The study underscores the importance of schools in fostering a healthy environment for their students and highlights the need for sustained efforts to support their mental well-being.

Adelman (2009) emphasized in his study on mental health in schools that psychosocial and mental health issues have a significant impact on students' academic performance. He stressed the critical role that schools play in supporting social-emotional development and learning, and the need to improve the availability and accessibility of mental health services for those who require them.

However, Slade (n.d.) expressed concerns regarding the quality and availability of mental health services offered in American schools. His research found that only half of middle and high schools in the United States provide mental health counseling services, while only 11% offer health counseling, physical exams, and substance abuse counseling. These findings underscore the need to increase efforts to provide mental health services in schools and address the barriers that hinder students' access to them.

Failure to consistently provide mental health services would also create barriers to seeking help to address mental health issues. Likewise, "normalizing" and toxic positivity may delay the identification and early diagnosis of mental disorder and may even aggravate the mental illness (Jorm, Angermeyer and Katschnig, 2000, Ines, 2019).

Furthermore, the lack of mental health programs in schools and communities may influence the level of mental health literacy and how students understand and respond to mental health conditions (Ines, 2019).

During the Covid 19 pandemic, school based mental health programs were implemented by DePEd, including psychosocial activities (Cruz, 2021). Among them is TALA: Tuklasin, Alamin, Likhain at Alalahanin for elementary learners which is an educational, child-friendly program that offers informative segments, storytelling, and art activities for children. For secondary learners they have OKKK! Tambayan (Online Kahusayan at Katatagan ng Kabataan) which is an online series that discusses mental health concerns with learners as student panelists and invited field experts. Both programs were livestreamed via the DepEd Philippines Facebook and Youtube channel. DepEd also have an inclusive program for the learners with disability and their parents and caregivers called Kakaiba-yanihan which is a psychosocial support service that focuses on values in building a supportive and caring environment for them. It aims to empower the children with disabilities and guide the parents and/or caregivers on how to effectively manage and support them especially in dealing with anxiety and stress. For the teaching and non-teaching personnel, they facilitated TAYO Naman!: Tulong,

Yakap at Oras para sa mga Tagapagtaguyod ng Edukasyon which was an online webinar that aimed to promote self-care during the pandemic (Malipot, 2021). Furthermore, aside from various psychosocial webinars, DepEd intensified the counseling and referral in public schools by formulating the counseling and referral system (Llego, 2021).

On the other hand, CHED also recognized the toll of the pandemic on the mental health of both the students and teachers. Aside from equipping the teachers with the necessary technological skills to shift to online learning, there were also program intended to take care of their mental well-being. Then CHED chief Prospero de Vera stressed the importance of taking care of the mental health not only of the students but also of the faculty members as 'anxiety, stress, and depression can reduce the capacity of the students and faculty members to adapt to the new normal (Handog, 2020).

The numerous advocacies opened the hearts, minds, and awareness of the Filipinos o to mental health. But are these enough? While there were policies in place a standard school mental health program is necessary to address the growing concern of mental health crisis in the Philippines. While most of the respondents who were interviewed expressed their appreciation of the psychological services offered in their university, the majority expressed that they want to see improvement in what they provide. There were many activities or mental health programs provided by DepEd and there were current studies recommending a school mental health program none have been standardized in the tertiary level.

6. Based on the results of the study, what School Mental Health Policy can be developed?

Despite the presence of various mental health programs in universities, there seems to be a noticeable gap indicating a potential lack of readiness on the part of universities to implement these programs effectively. Although quantitative results indicate high levels of mental health literacy among students, qualitative data highlights areas for improvement in the mental health services and programs offered by universities. To bridge this gap, a proposed mental health policy has been developed, drawing upon the principles of mental health literacy theory and considering the expressed needs of the participants.

The development of the proposed mental health policy was guided by the shared experiences and expressed needs of the respondents, who emphasized the importance of having a comprehensive mental health program with appropriate personnel and services. This policy, named GINHAWA, is centered around the concept of mental health literacy.

The term "GINHAWA" is derive from Tagalog, meaning "relief" or "comfort" in English. It encapsulates the idea of finding relief or comfort in both physical and emotional well-being, such as experiencing a sense of relief from challenging situations or finding solace in times of distress. The GINHAWA program aims to enhance mental health literacy among all school stakeholders, equipping them with the necessary knowledge and skills to promote well-being.

One of the primary goals of the program is to address and reduce stigma and discrimination surrounding mental health. By challenging misconceptions and stereotypes, the program seeks to foster a more understanding and accepting environment. It aims to create a shift in attitudes and perceptions, promoting empathy and compassion towards individuals experiencing mental health challenges.

Furthermore, the GINHAWA program aims to enhance help-seeking behaviors and psychological first-aid skills among school stakeholders. By increasing their knowledge and understanding of mental health, individuals will be better equipped to recognize signs of distress and provide appropriate support. This includes promoting a culture of seeking help when needed and ensuring that individuals feel comfortable reaching out for support.

Ultimately, the GINHAWA program aims to empower school stakeholders, eliminate stigma and discrimination, and foster an environment that promotes mental well-being. By improving mental health literacy and enhancing help-seeking skills, the program seeks to create a supportive community where individuals can find relief and comfort in times of mental health challenges.

Taking into consideration the practical limitations faced by some schools and universities in terms of resources and mental health services, the development of this policy acknowledges the need for a realistic approach. In contrast to idealistic suggestions, the GINHAWA policy emphasizes the utilization of available resources, fostering a sense of teamwork among all school stakeholders.

By adopting this approach, the policy aims to ensure consistency and availability of a range of mental health services for university stakeholders. Rather than striving for unattainable goals, the focus is on leveraging existing resources and fostering collaboration among different members of the school community. This approach recognizes the importance of collective effort and utilizing available support systems to promote the well-being of all university stakeholders.

In essence, the GINHAWA policy seeks to optimize the utilization of resources within the given context, promoting a collaborative and inclusive approach to mental health support. By doing so, it strives to provide consistent and accessible mental health services for the university community, acknowledging the realities and constraints faced by schools and universities while still working towards the promotion of mental well-being.

The GINHAWA Program: Generating Initiatives to Nurture Hope, Awareness, Well-being, and Acceptance is a proposed mental health program designed to promote increased mental health literacy, increase mental health awareness, nurture hope and well-being, and encourage acceptance through sustainable and effective school mental health services.

It is guided by the following objectives:

- Increase mental health awareness;
- Correct erroneous beliefs and stereotypes related to mental health;
- Acquire the ability to help and seek help;
- Understand the concepts of mental health illnesses and psychotherapy or clinical management, and eradicate stigma and discrimination towards people with mental health issues

GINHAWA SCHOOL MENTAL HEALTH POLICY

Mental Health is a state of well-being in which the individual realizes one's own abilities and potentials, copes adequately with the normal stresses of life, displays resilience in the face of extreme life events, work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a positive contribution to the community (RA 10036). In compliance with RA 11036 or the Mental Health Act, this School Mental Health policy aims to serve as a framework for school stakeholders in addressing mental health-related situations.

The GINHAWA is an acronym for Generating Initiatives to Nurture Hope Awareness Well-being and Acceptance is a proposed mental health policy designed to promote increased mental health literacy, increase mental health awareness, nurture hope and well-being, and encourage acceptance through a consistent and effective school mental health activities. This policy aims to promote positive mental health for every school stakeholder. Furthermore, this policy aims to promote a safe and caring environment for school stakeholders who may directly or indirectly be affected by mental health concerns.

SCOPE

This policy describes the university's approach to promoting positive mental health and is intended as guidance for all school staff-teaching, non-teaching, and administrators.

This policy should be read in conjunction with the Student Manual and Manual for faculty and employees where a stakeholder's mental health condition overlaps or is linked with medical, behavioral, or other school rules that need to be identified as a special educational need.

POLICY OBJECTIVES:

This policy aims to:

- Cultivate positive mental health in all school stakeholders
- Increase mental health literacy;
- Correct the erroneous beliefs and stereotypes related to mental health;
- Acquire the ability to help others and seek help;
- Provide support to stakeholders suffering from mental health illnesses and also to their peers, and loved ones
- Understand the concepts of mental health illnesses and psychotherapy or clinical management
- Eradicate or lessen the stigma and discrimination toward people with mental health

Conclusion

This study examined the mental health literacy and mental health programs and services and was conducted in different universities in Metro Manila with 342 students, 48 faculty, 44 employees, and 8 administrators as participants. After a thorough analysis on the gathered data, it is therefore concluded that (1) The findings of the study indicate that students, employees, faculty, and administrators possess high to very high levels of mental health literacy.

This suggests that there is a commendable understanding of mental health problems, as well as knowledge of appropriate help-seeking behaviors, self-help strategies, and the ability to dispel erroneous beliefs or stereotypes. These results highlight the positive impact of mental health awareness efforts within educational institutions. However, it is important to continuously promote and reinforce mental health literacy to ensure the well-being and support of all stakeholders. (2) There is no difference in the level of mental health literacy of students, employees, faculty and administrators. This indicates that the efforts to promote mental health awareness and provide educational activities have been effective in increasing mental health literacy among the stakeholders. The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic has further emphasized the importance of mental health, leading to heightened awareness and understanding. These findings highlight the progress made in addressing mental health issues in the academic setting through advocacy and educational initiatives. Continued efforts to promote mental health literacy will be crucial in sustaining this positive momentum and ensuring the well-being of individuals within the academic community. (3) There is a discrepancy between the quantitative results indicating high levels of mental health literacy as measured by the Mental Health Literacy Questionnaire and the qualitative findings that highlight the need for improvement and sustainability of mental health services and programs.

While the participants demonstrated a commendable level of mental health literacy based on the questionnaire, their experiences and suggestions emphasized the importance of ongoing efforts to enhance mental health support. The study underscores the need to go beyond quantitative measures and consider the experiential and qualitative aspects of mental health. It highlights the importance of

continuously improving and sustaining mental health services and programs to meet the evolving needs and experiences of individuals in order to bridge the gap between high levels of mental health literacy and the actual support required. (4) The mental health services provided in the universities differ from each university category

The study highlights the need for a mental health policy with tailored approaches to mental health support based on the specific characteristics and resources available in each university category. Understanding these differences can aid in the development of targeted interventions and strategies to address the unique mental health needs of students, faculty, employees, and administrators in each university setting. By recognizing and addressing these variations, universities can enhance the effectiveness and inclusivity of their mental health services, promoting the well-being of their respective university communities. (5) There is a need for more sustainable implementation of a mental health services. The participants' suggestions and feedback highlight the importance of continuous efforts to enhance and maintain mental health programs and support systems. This includes ensuring consistent delivery of services, expanding available resources, and promoting long-term commitment to mental health initiatives. By addressing these recommendations, universities can create a more supportive and resilient environment that effectively addresses the mental health needs of their stakeholders. It is crucial to prioritize sustainability to foster lasting improvements in mental health services and promote the overall well-being of individuals within the university community. (6) A proposed school mental health policy is needed. Although some of the participants expressed favorable feedback regarding the psychological services provided by their university, there remains a clear need for improvement. The participants highlighted the importance of enhancing mental health services and available resources, which may hinder the effectiveness of the mental health programs. It is important to acknowledge that not all universities have the capacity to implement idealistic mental health programs as suggested in prior studies. Therefore, the researcher recommends the implementation of a school- mental health policy, known as the GINHAWA. This program goes beyond knowledge dissemination and focuses on correcting erroneous beliefs and stereotypes through mental health awareness campaigns. Creating a policy, rather than just a program, offers several advantages in addressing mental health. It provides a formal framework for consistency, institutionalizes mental health efforts, ensures resource allocation and accountability, and promotes compliance with laws and standards. A policy-based approach supports long-term commitment, integration, and sustainability of mental health initiatives within an organization.

Based on the study findings, several key recommendations emerge to improve mental health services and support within universities.

(1) Continuous promotion and reinforcement of mental health literacy among students, employees, faculty, and administrators to ensure ongoing well-being and support. (2) Considering the use of a different mental health literacy tool or assessment to validate the results and obtain a more comprehensive understanding of mental health literacy. Different tools may capture additional dimensions or nuances of mental health literacy that were not captured in the current study. (3) Include more participants to normalize the distribution per group. Expanding the participant pool by including a larger and more diverse sample can enhance the generalizability and reliability of the results. Including participants from different backgrounds and educational institutions can provide a more representative picture of mental health literacy across a broader population. These will help to refine the assessment and broaden the understanding of mental health literacy among university stakeholders. (4) Conducting a comprehensive assessment, developing standardized guidelines, fostering collaboration, and establishing partnerships to enhance the quality and equity of mental health services. (5) Prioritize long-term planning, resource allocation, and ongoing support to ensure the continued effectiveness and availability of mental health services in the university setting. (6) Consider the adoption and implementation of the GINHAWA Mental Health Policy as a strategic approach to enhance mental health services and support within the university. This policy provides a comprehensive framework for addressing mental health concerns, promoting sustainability, and ensuring the well-being of all stakeholders. (7) Use the study findings as a foundation for future research in areas such as the impact of mental health programs on academic performance, effectiveness of interventions, experiences of marginalized groups, and long-term outcomes of comprehensive mental health policies. This will contribute to a deeper understanding of mental health in educational contexts and inform evidence-based practices for supporting well-being.

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